

2-(2-Hydroxy)phenylazo derivatives of some 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes

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Abstract : 2-Hydroxyphenylazo derivatives of three 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds (acetylacetone, methylacetoacetate and acetoacetanilide) have been synthesized and characterised. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data indicate that the compounds exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded keto-hydrazone form. Dibasic tridentate coordination of these compounds in their [M₂L₂] complexes (M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) has been established on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

Keywords : 2-Hydroxyphenylazo derivatives, phenyl hydrazones, keto-hydrazone, metal complexes.

Introduction

The importance of hydrogen bonding and tautomerism in arylazo compounds having hydroxyl groups adjacent to azo functions has been well documented¹⁻³. Presence of such metallizable substituents at suitable positions markedly influences the coordination characteristics of azodyes¹⁻⁴. The coupling of diazonium salts, containing additional metal binding sites at *ortho* position, with the active methylene group of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds result in the formation of multidentate azo/hydrazone ligand systems. In continuation of our studies on arylazo⁵⁻⁹ derivatives of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes, we here report the synthesis and characterization of 2-hydroxyphenylazo derivatives of three 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds : acetylacetone, methylacetoacetate and acetoacetanilide. Typical metal complexes of these compounds were also synthesized and characterized.

Results and discussion

Elemental analytical data of the 2-hydroxyphenylhydrazones (Table 1) indicate that coupling between diazotised *o*-aminophenol and 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds has occurred in the 1 : 1 ratio. All the compounds are crystalline in nature and are soluble in common organic solvents. They formed stable complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}

and Zn^{II} ions. The analytical data (Table 1) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF (specific conductance < 10 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) suggest [M₂L₂] stoichiometry of the complexes except for the Ni^{II} complexes which have [Ni₂L₂(H₂O)₄] stoichiometry. The Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The observed electronic, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of H₂hpa and H₂hma are in conformity with structure 1 and their complexes with structure 2. Analytical and spectral data of H₂han are in agreement with structure 3 and its complexes with structure 4.

Infrared spectra : The IR spectra of H₂hpa and H₂hma in the 1600–1800 cm⁻¹ region showed strong bands at

1

Compd.	R
H ₂ hpa	-CH ₃
H ₂ hma	-OCH ₃

M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}
 (The Ni^{II} complexes contain two coordinated H₂O molecules on each Ni²⁺ ions)

2

3

M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}
 (The Ni^{II} complex contain two coordinated H₂O molecules on each Ni²⁺ ions)

4

1680 and 1725 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching of free acetyl and ester carbonyls respectively^{7,8}. The spectra also showed a strong band at ~1630 cm⁻¹ and a medium

intensity band at ~1615 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl and C=N vibrations^{10,11} of structure 1. The broad band in the range 2500–3300 cm⁻¹ indicates the existence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these compounds. In the spectra of all the complexes the free carbonyl and C=N bands remained almost unaffected indicating their non-involvement in complexation. However the band due to the hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl at ~1630 cm⁻¹ of the ligands disappeared and instead a new strong band appeared at ~1570 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl group as in structure 2. The broad band in the range 2500–3300 cm⁻¹ of the ligands disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes and bands due to various νC–H vibrations appeared in the region.

The IR spectrum of H₂han in the 1650–1800 cm⁻¹ region does not show any band assignable to free carbonyl group. However the spectrum showed two strong bands at 1648 and 1635 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded anilide and acetyl carbonyl groups respectively^{7,8} of structure 3. The spectrum also showed a medium intensity band at 1620 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of C=N vibration^{10,11}. The broad band in the range 2500–3200 cm⁻¹ indicates the existence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the compound. In the spectra of all the complexes the acetyl carbonyl and C=N bands remained almost unaffected indicating their non-involvement in complexation. However the band due to the hydrogen bonded anilide carbonyl at 1648 cm⁻¹ disappeared and instead a new strong band appeared at ~1560 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl group as in structure 4. As in the ligand spectrum the complexes showed a band at ~3380 cm⁻¹ due to NH group of anilide.

The spectra of all the ligands showed several medium intensity bands in the range 1580–1600 cm⁻¹ due to various C=C vibrations. Absence of any band assignable to N=N in the region 1400–1500 cm⁻¹ and the presence of a medium intensity band at ~1525 cm⁻¹ due to deformation vibration of NH group further support hydrazone form of the compounds. The band at ~1525 cm⁻¹ of the ligands due to νN–H vibration disappeared in the spectra

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of H₂hpa, H₂hma, H₂han and their metal complexes

Compd./ Molecular formula	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
			Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
H ₂ hpa	55	240	60.11 (60.00)	5.44 (5.45)	12.78 (12.73)	-
C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃						
H ₂ hma	60	205	55.80 (55.93)	5.07 (5.08)	11.75 (11.86)	-
C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄						
H ₂ han	60	206	64.67 (64.65)	5.02 (5.05)	14.01 (14.14)	-
C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃						
[Ni ₂ (hpa) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	60	>360	42.29 (42.21)	4.46 (4.48)	8.84 (8.95)	18.74 (18.77)
C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ Ni ₂ O ₁₀						
[Ni ₂ (hma) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	62	286	40.24 (40.16)	4.23 (4.26)	8.48 (8.52)	17.92 (17.86)
C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ Ni ₂ O ₁₂						
[Ni ₂ (han) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	70	285	49.33 (49.27)	4.34 (4.36)	10.74 (10.78)	15.12 (15.07)
C ₃₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ Ni ₂ O ₁₀						
[Cu ₂ (hpa) ₂]	65	300	46.76 (46.88)	3.51 (3.55)	10.02 (9.95)	22.45 (22.57)
C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cu ₂ N ₄ O ₆						
[Cu ₂ (hma) ₂]	70	>360	44.22 (44.36)	3.36 (3.36)	9.36 (9.41)	21.48 (21.36)
C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cu ₂ N ₄ O ₈						
[Cu ₂ (han) ₂]	70	>360	53.52 (53.55)	3.60 (3.63)	11.64 (11.71)	17.60 (17.72)
C ₃₂ H ₂₆ Cu ₂ N ₆ O ₆						
[Zn ₂ (hpa) ₂]	68	>360	46.50 (46.58)	3.53 (3.53)	9.80 (9.88)	23.11 (23.07)
C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ Zn ₂						
[Zn ₂ (hma) ₂]	70	280	44.04 (44.09)	3.32 (3.34)	9.29 (9.35)	21.78 (21.84)
C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₈ Zn ₂						
[Zn ₂ (han) ₂]	65	300	53.32 (53.28)	3.64 (3.61)	11.54 (11.65)	18.02 (18.14)
C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₆ Zn ₂						

of all the complexes indicating the replacement of the hydrazone NH proton by metal ion during complexation. The spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show bands due to coordinated water at ~3450 cm⁻¹. The νC=O frequency of the ligands at ~1240 cm⁻¹ is shifted to higher value (by ~25 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of all the complexes typical of bridging phenolate oxygen. A new medium intensity band observed at ~550 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the chelates can be assigned to νM-N vibration¹². The involvement of intramolecularly hydrogen bonded carbonyl oxygen and phenolic oxygen in complexation is clearly evident from the appearance of two additional medium intensity bands at ~430 and ~475 cm⁻¹ assignable to νM-O vibrations¹². Important bands that appeared in the spectra are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristic IR stretching bands (cm⁻¹) of H₂hpa, H₂hma, H₂han and their metal complexes

Compd.	Free Chelated				
	(C=O)	(C=O)	(C=N)	(M-N)	(M-O)
H ₂ hpa	1680	1628	1615	-	-
[Ni ₂ (hpa) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	1674	1557	1610	542	478, 422
[Cu ₂ (hpa) ₂]	1676	1558	1612	548	472, 428
[Zn ₂ (hpa) ₂]	1678	1565	1612	550	468, 430
H ₂ hma	1725	1625	1612	-	-
[Ni ₂ (hma) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	1718	1575	1610	545	472, 432
[Cu ₂ (hma) ₂]	1722	1577	1610	540	465, 435
[Zn ₂ (hma) ₂]	1720	1564	1608	530	480, 420
H ₂ han	-	1648, 1635	1620	-	-
[Ni ₂ (han) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	-	1565, 1634	1612	545	475, 425
[Cu ₂ (han) ₂]	-	1558, 1635	1614	548	476, 425
[Zn ₂ (han) ₂]	-	1568, 1632	1616	546	480, 430

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds are characterized by the presence of two low field one proton signals at ~δ 15 and ~δ 10 ppm due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded N-H and O-H protons^{13,14}. The anilide NH proton signal of H₂han is observed at 11.48 ppm. The integrated intensities of all the signals agree well with the structures 1 and 3 of the compounds. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Zn^{II} complexes, the low field signals due to the chelated hydrogens disappeared indicating the replacement of hydrazone and phenolic protons by metal ion during complexation¹⁵. The ester carbonyl group of H₂hma and anilide NH group of H₂han are excluded from coordination and is evident from the observed position of the OCH₃ and anilide NH resonance signals which remain unaltered. The chelate of H₂hpa shows two methyl proton signals of equal intensity indicating that the two acetyl groups are in different chemical environment. The position of the methyl proton signals in H₂han indicates that the acetyl carbonyl is not involved in complexation. Integrated intensities of all other protons agree well with the structures 2 and 4 of the complexes. The assignments of various proton signals observed are given in Table 3.

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data (δ, ppm) of H₂hpa, H₂hma, H₂han and their Zn^{II} complexes

Compd.	CH ₃ CO	RCO	Phenyl	OH	NH
H ₂ hpa	2.54 (3H, s)	2.46 (3H, s)	6.90-7.03 (4H, m)	10.14 (1H, s)	15.19 (1H, s, br)
[Zn ₂ (hpa) ₂]	2.88 (6H, s)	2.42 (6H, s)	6.81-7.11 (8H, m)	-	-
H ₂ hma	2.50 (3H, s)	3.70 (3H, s)	6.86-7.00 (4H, m)	10.66 (1H, s)	14.91 (1H, s, br)
[Zn ₂ (hma) ₂]	2.95 (6H, s)	3.76 (6H, s)	6.85-7.10 (8H, m)	-	-
					14.71
H ₂ han	2.58 (3H, s)	6.90-7.15 (5H, m)	7.41-7.66 (4H, m)	10.00 (1H, s)	11.48 ^a (1H, s)
[Zn ₂ (han) ₂]	2.60 (6H, s)	6.90-7.13 (10H, m)	7.45-7.60 (8H, m)	-	11.44 ^a (2H, s)

^adue to anilide NH, s = singlet, m = multiplet, br = broad.

Mass spectra : The formulation of the compounds as in structures 1 and 3 is clearly supported from the presence of intense molecular ion peak in the mass spectra.

Since peaks due to the elimination of ArN₂^{16,17}, a characteristic feature of the azo tautomer, have not been observed in the mass spectra indicate the existence of the compounds in the hydrazone form. The spectra of all the compounds show an intense peak at m/z 108 due to the formation of C₆H₄(OH)NH⁺ through the cleavage of N-N bond thereby confirming their keto-hydrazone tautomeric structure. The formation of other important peaks is due to the elimination of CH₃CO, RCO, C₆H₅NHCO etc. from the molecular ion or subsequent fragments. The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks of appreciable intensity corresponding to [Cu₂L₂] stoichiometry indicating their existence in the bridged dimeric structure as in structures 2 and 4. Peaks corresponding to the elimination of CH₃CO, RCO, C₆H₅NHCO, dicarbonyl moieties etc. from the molecular ion are also present in the spectra. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes (Table 4).

Table 4. Mass spectral data of H₂hpa, H₂hma, H₂han and their Cu^{II} complexes

Compd.	Mass spectral data (m/z)
H ₂ hpa	220, 177, 134, 112, 108
H ₂ hma	236, 193, 177, 134, 128, 108
H ₂ han	297, 254, 189, 177, 134, 120, 108
[Cu ₂ (hpa) ₂]	566, 564, 562, 523, 521, 519, 480, 478, 476, 283, 281, 220, 134, 108
[Cu ₂ (hma) ₂]	598, 596, 594, 539, 537, 535, 480, 478, 476, 299, 297, 236, 193, 177, 108
[Cu ₂ (han) ₂]	720, 718, 716, 677, 675, 673, 634, 632, 630, 360, 358, 297, 177, 134, 120, 108

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the compounds show two broad bands with maxima at ~390 nm and ~260 nm due to various n→π* and π→π* transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad visible band, λ_{max} at ~15000 cm⁻¹. This, together with the measured μ_{eff} values (1.75-1.80 BM) suggests the square-planar geometry¹⁸. The Ni^{II} chelates are paramagnetic (μ_{eff}, ~2.80 BM) and show three well-separated absorption bands in the spectra at λ_{max} ~8200, ~13450 and ~24400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions; ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}; ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P) respec-

tively. These indicate the existence of the metal ions in a square planar environment with one nitrogen and three oxygen atoms of the ligand, and the two water molecules occupy *trans* positions of an overall octahedral structure. The presence of shoulders in the spectra are due to the additional transitions of the dimeric structure.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by microanalyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds in methanol (10^{-4} mol/L) were recorded on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr discs) on an 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF ($\sim 10^{-3}$ mol/L) at 28 ± 1 °C. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of 2-hydroxyphenylhydrazones, H₂hpa, H₂hma and H₂han : *o*-Aminophenol was diazotised as reported¹⁹. After destroying the excess nitrous acid with urea, the diazonium salt solution (0.01 mol) was added drop by drop with stirring to an ice-cold methanolic solution of the 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (0.01 mol, 50 mL). Concentrated sodium acetate solution was simultaneously added to control the pH of the solution between 6 and 8. The yellow precipitate formed was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from hot ethanol to get chromatographically pure (TLC) material.

Synthesis of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes : A solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol) in minimum amount of water was added to a solution of the ligand in methanol (0.01 mol, 25 mL). The mixed solution was refluxed on a boiling water bath for ~ 1 h and then cooled to room temperature. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from hot methanol.

Conclusion :

A new series of tridentate ligand systems have been prepared by the coupling of diazotised *o*-aminophenol with acetylacetone, methylacetoacetate and acetoacetanilide. Analytical, IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectral data

revealed a 1 : 1 product in which one of the carbonyl group of the dicarbonyl compound is involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the hydrazone hydrogen. Analytical, physical and spectral data of their $[\text{Ni}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ complexes with Ni^{II} and $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2]$ complexes with Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} showed the dibasic tridentate coordination involving one of the hydrazone nitrogen, phenolate oxygen and one of the carbonyl oxygen resulting in the formation of two annulated chelate rings with the dimeric structure in which the phenolate oxygen bridges between two metal ions. In the metal complexes of the azo derivatives of acetylacetone and methylacetoacetate, the acetyl carbonyl is involved in coordination where as in the chelates of the azo derivative of acetoacetanilide, the anilide carbonyl is bonded with the metal ion.

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